

Synthesis of Some Substituted Homophthalic Acids

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6-Methoxy-3-methyl- and 4,5-dimethoxy-homophthalic acids have been prepared in good yields from 3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid and veratric acid, respectively, in three simple stages.

The constitutions of the homophthalic acids, reported by Meldrum and Kapadia as 4-hydroxy-5-methyl- (m.p. 209°) and 6-hydroxy-5-methyl-homophthalic acids (m.p. 212-13°), have been revised and the constitutions of 4-methoxy-5-methyl- (m.p. 209°) and 4-hydroxy-5-methyl-homophthalic acid (m.p. 212-13°), respectively, have been assigned to them.

Synthesis of 4-methoxy- and 4-hydroxy-homophthalic acids from *m*-methoxy- and *m*-hydroxy-benzoic acid, respectively, in excellent yields was reported earlier¹. Adopting a similar procedure, 6-methoxy-3-methyl- (IVa) and 4,5-dimethoxy-homophthalic acids (IVc) have now been synthesised in quite good yields from 3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid (Ia) and veratric acid (Ic), respectively.

3-Methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid (Ia) was condensed with chloral hydrate in presence of 95% sulphuric acid when 3-trichloromethyl-4-methoxy-7-methylphthalide (IIa) was obtained. Its constitution follows from the fact that there is only one position, *i.e.*, position 2 of the acid (Ia), which is available for the chloral hydrate to condense. The yield of trichloromethylphthalide (IIa) was 50% under the best experimental conditions. The low yield may be ascribed to the steric effect of -OMe group in position 3 of the acid (Ia). The trichloromethylphthalide (IIa) was reduced with zinc and glacial acetic acid when 2-($\beta\beta$ dichloroethyl)-3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid (IIIa) was obtained. The reduction, however, did not furnish good yields of the acid (IIIa) (54.5%). This may be due to the steric effect of the methoxyl group in position 3 of the phthalide(IIa) which hinders the reduction of the proximal -CCl₂ group. The dichloro compound (IIIa) was then hydrolysed and oxidised by treating with 90% sulphuric acid when 6-methoxy-3-methylhomophthalic acid (IVa) was obtained in 45% yield. The overall yield of the homophthalic acid (IVa), calculated from (Ia), is 28% of the theoretical.

The attempts to synthesise 6-hydroxy-3-methylhomophthalic acid (IVb) directly from 3-hydroxy-6-methylbenzoic acid (Ib), however, did not meet with success. The acid (Ib) condensed with chloral hydrate very readily in presence of sulphuric acid with 60% yield of 3-trichloromethyl-4-hydroxy-7-methylphthalide (IIb). The methyl ether of (IIb) was prepared by using dimethyl sulphate and alkali and was indentified as (IIa) by mixed m.p. with the previous specimen, remaining undepressed. The reduction of (IIb) with zinc and acetic acid provided a product which was insoluble in sodium bicarbonate solution and also could not be obtained in a pure state.

The synthesis of 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (IVc) from 6-methoxy-1-hydrindone² involves a number of steps and the overall yield of the homophthalic acid (IVc) is very poor². This homophthalic acid (IVc) has now been synthesised from veratric acid (Ic) in excellent yield in three simple stages by a procedure similar to that described earlier¹.

Veratric acid (Ic) on condensation with chloral hydrate in presence of sulphuric acid, according to Meldrum and Parikh³, furnished 3-trichloromethyl-5,6-dimethoxyphthalide (IIc) which on reduction with zinc and acetic acid, according to the same authors, furnished 2-($\beta\beta$ dichloroethyl)-4,5-dimethoxybenzoic acid (IIIc). The experimental procedure adopted by Meldrum and Parikh³ was standardised to obtain optimum yields. Very high yields of the products were obtained in both stages of the reaction. The dichloro compound (IIIc) was hydrolysed and oxidised by treating it with 90% sulphuric acid in the usual manner when 4,5-dimethoxyhomophthalic acid (IVc) was obtained in 90% yield. The overall yield of the homophthalic acid (IVc), calculated from veratric acid (Ic), is 56% of the theory. This method for the synthesis of (IVc) is far superior to the one known in the literature².

The formation of 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe) by the action of sulphuric acid on 2-($\beta\beta$ -dichloroethyl)-5-methoxy-4-methylbenzoic acid (IIIId) was reported by Meldrum and Kapadia⁴. These authors⁴ assumed that besides the normal action of sulphuric acid to hydrolyse and oxidise the dichloro compound (IIIId), it also demethylated the methoxyl group during the reaction. This is surprising as such a type of demethylation has not been observed by the present workers in the other similar cases¹. The dichloro compound (IIIId) was therefore prepared according to them, by first condensing 3-methoxy-4-methylbenzoic acid (Id) with chloral hydrate and the resulting 3-trichloromethyl-6-methoxy-5-methylphthalide (IIIId) was reduced with zinc and acetic acid to furnish

2. Perkin and Robinson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, **91**, 1073; Chakravarti and Swaminathan, *this Journal*, 1935, **11**, 101.

3. *Proc. Ind. Acad. Sci.*, 1935, **1A**, 431.

4. *This Journal*, 1932, **9**, 483.

(IIIId). On treating (IIIId) with sulphuric acid in the usual manner, the acid with the same m.p. (209°), as reported by them, was obtained. The elementary analysis of this acid, however, did not agree with that of 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe), as stated by the authors⁴, but agreed very well with that of 4-methoxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVd) (the product which could have been normally expected). Its equivalent weight (116) also agreed with that of (IVd). The equivalent weight (210) reported⁴ is actually the molecular weight of 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe). This is surprising as the homophthalic acid is a dibasic acid. Further, the homophthalic acid derivative (m.p. 209°) was successfully demethylated to provide the corresponding hydroxy-acid (IVe; m.p. 213-14°). This acid developed the characteristic colour with aqueous ferric chloride, but the original acid (m.p. 209°) formed only a buff-coloured precipitate. These facts indicate clearly that the presumption of Meldrum and Kapadia⁴ of demethylation occurring during the treatment of (IIIId) with sulphuric acid is not correct. The constitution of 4-methoxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVd) is therefore assigned to the acid (m.p. 209°), which was described by Meldrum and Kapadia⁴ as 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe), and the demethylated product (m.p. 213-14°) is assigned the constitution of 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe).

All the stages for the synthesis of the homophthalic acid (IVd) from 3-methoxy-4-methylbenzoic acid (Id) were standardised to obtain best yields. The overall yield of the homophthalic acid (IVd), calculated from the acid (Id), is 30% of the theory.

The synthesis of 6-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVf) was reported by Meldrum and Kapadia⁴. They condensed 3-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid (Ie) with chloral hydrate and the resulting trichloromethylphthalide derivative was reduced with zinc and acetic acid to a dichloro compound which was treated with sulphuric acid in the usual manner to yield the homophthalic acid derivative. This procedure can lead (*vide infra*) to the formation of either 6-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVf) by route A or to 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe) by route B, depending on the position where chloral hydrate condenses in the first stage of the reaction.

These authors⁴ assumed the reaction to take place by route A because the mixed m.p. of the final product (i.e. the homophthalic acid derivative) with the homophthalic acid (m.p. 209°), which they had prepared from (Id) and which they believed to be 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe), was lowered, thus showing the two compounds to be different. The homophthalic acid derivative (m.p. 209°), which Meldrum and Kapadia⁴ considered as 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe), is actually 4-methoxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVd). During the present investigation, the homophthalic acid derivative (m. p. 213-14°) was synthesised from 3-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid (Ie) according to these authors⁴ and was methylated with dimethyl sulphate and alkali. The mixed m.p. of this methyl ether (m.p. 209°) with 4-methoxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVd) (m.p. 209°). (*vide supra*) remaining undepressed indisputably shows the identity of this methyl ether as 4-methoxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid and therefore the original homophthalic acid⁴ that was obtained is 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe). This was further confirmed by the fact that the mixed m.p. of this homophthalic acid with the demethylated product of 4-methoxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVd) was not depressed.

The homophthalic acid (m.p. 213-14°), described by Meldrum and Kapadia⁴ as 6-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVf), is therefore now assigned the constitution of 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe). This further leads to the revision of the constitution of all the intermediates, as it is quite clear that the synthesis has followed the route B. The compound⁴, reported as 2-trichloromethyl-4-hydroxy-5-methylphthalide (IIIf), is therefore assigned the constitution of 3-trichloromethyl-6-hydroxy-5-methylphthalide (IIe). This is in agreement with the normal expectation that chloral hydrate will condense in position 6 in preference to position 2 of the acid (Ie), as the latter position is relatively less accessible. The reduced product, reported by them as 2-($\beta\beta$ -dichloroethyl)-3-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid⁴ (IIIIf), is now assigned the constitution of 2-($\beta\beta$ -dichloroethyl)-5-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid (IIIe).

All the stages for the synthesis of 4-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe) from 3-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid (Ie) were standardised to obtain the best yields. The overall yield of the homophthalic acid derivative (IVe), calculated from the acid (Ie), is 36% of the theory.

EXPERIMENTAL

3-Trichloromethyl-4-methoxy-7-methylphthalide (IIa). — 3-Methoxy-6-methylbenzoic acid⁵ (Ia) (6 g.), chloral hydrate (4.4 g.), and H₂SO₄ (27 ml, 95%) were mixed and the reaction mixture was shaken well till most of the solid dissolved. It was kept at the room temperature (28-30°) for 40 hr. and then poured on crushed ice. The product separating was triturated with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove the unchanged acid (Ia), filtered, washed with water, dried, and crystallised from acetic acid (80%) as colorless shining plates, m.p. 134-35°, yield 5 g. (Found: C, 44.70; H, 3.30. C₁₁H₉O₃Cl₃ requires C, 44.48; H, 3.04%). Recovered yield of (Ia) was 2 g.

2-($\beta\beta$ -Dichloroethyl)-3-methoxy-6-methylbenzoic Acid (IIIa).—To the phthalide (IIa) (5 g.), dissolved in hot glacial acetic acid (31 ml) and mechanically stirred, zinc dust (4.5 g.) was added in small portions during 30 min. Stirring was continued for about an hour after the addition was complete. It was then just heated on a water bath and filtered hot from zinc acetate. The filtrate was diluted with water and the solid separating was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution; the pasty mass remaining insoluble was removed. It was then reprecipitated and crystallised from petroleum (b.p. 80-100°) in clusters of tiny needles, m.p. 135-36°, yield 2.5 g. (Found: C, 50.1; H, 4.5. $C_{11}H_{12}O_3Cl_2$ requires C, 50.4; H, 4.6%).

6-Methoxy-3-methylhomophthalic Acid (IVa).—The dichloro compound (IIIa) (3 g.) was added in small lots to H_2SO_4 (21 ml, 90%) with constant shaking. The reaction mixture was occasionally heated on a water bath. The addition of (IIIa) was so adjusted that the second lot was added only after the first lot had dissolved completely. After the addition was complete (ca. $\frac{1}{2}$ hr.), the reaction mixture was heated on a water bath at about 65-70° till no more hydrogen chloride had evolved (ca. 3-4 hr.). It was poured on crushed ice when a small amount of a solid product separated. It was taken in ether, saturated with sodium chloride, and repeatedly extracted with ether. After removal of the ether, the oily residue was washed with hot toluene when a solid separated. It was crystallised from boiling toluene in shining plates, m.p. 162-63°, yield 1.2 g. (Found: C, 58.90; H, 5.40. $C_{11}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 58.93; H, 5.36%).

3-Trichloromethyl-4-hydroxy-7-methylphthalide (IIb).—3-Hydroxy-6-methylbenzoic acid⁵ (Ib) (12.1 g.), chloral hydrate (19 g.) and H_2SO_4 (67 ml, 95%) were mixed and shaken well to a homogeneous solution. After keeping the reaction mixture at the room temperature for 40 hr., it was worked up as described in the case of (IIa). It was crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 192-93°, yield 14 g. (Found: C, 42.90; H, 2.80. $C_{10}H_7O_3Cl_3$ requires C, 42.85; H, 2.50%).

Methyl Ether (IIa).—The phthalide (IIb) (2.8 g.) was dissolved in aqueous $NaOH$ (8 ml, 10%) and the solution was cooled in ice-cold water. To this dimethyl sulphate (1.5 ml) and aqueous $NaOH$ solution (8 ml, 10%) were added alternately in small portions with vigorous shaking and cooling. The solution was maintained alkaline during the reaction. The product separating slowly was crystallised from acetic acid (80%) in shining plates, m.p. 134-35°, yield 2 g. Mixed m.p. with the the authentic specimen of (IIa), obtained from (Ia), remained undepressed.

3-Trichloromethyl-5,6-dimethoxyphthalide (IIc).—Veratric acid⁶ (Ic) (9.1 g.), chloral hydrate (16.4 g.) and H_2SO_4 (37 ml, 98%) were mixed, warmed slightly to form a homogeneous solution, and left at the room temperature for 65 hr. The product separating after pouring the mixture on crushed ice was triturated with sodium bicarbonate solution to remove the unchanged veratric acid. It was crystallised from aqueous acetone in tiny prisms, m.p. 146°, yield 5 g. (Meldrum and Parikh³ reported the same m.p.). (Found: C, 42.70; H, 3.00. Calc. for $C_{11}H_9O_4Cl_3$: C, 42.58; H, 2.90%). Recovered yield of (Ic) was 6g.

2-($\beta\beta$ -Dichloroethyl)-4,5-dimethoxybenzoic acid (IIIc) was prepared by reduction of (IIc) (5 g.) with zinc dust (4.5 g.) and glacial acetic acid (50 ml). The reduction was carried out as described in the case of (IIIa). The product separating on dilution was

6. Berger and Silberschmidt, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 2024.

crystallised from benzene in silky needles, m.p. 201°, yield 3 g. (Meldrum and Parikh³ reported the same m.p.). (Found: C, 47.30; H, 4.50. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_4Cl_2$: C, 47.49; H, 4.32%).

4,5-Dimethoxyhomophthalic Acid (IVc).—Compound (IIIc) (3 g.) was added in small lots to 90% H_2SO_4 (21 ml) with constant shaking. The same precautions as described in the case of (IVa) were followed during the addition and the reaction was completed in the same manner. It was then poured on crushed ice. The solid separating was first boiled with chloroform to remove the unchanged (IIIc). It was crystallised from water (charcoal) in shining plates, m.p. 215-16° (decomp.), yield 1.8 g. (lit.³ m.p. 214-15°). (Found: C, 55.2; H, 5.4. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{12}O_6$: C, 55.0; H, 5.0%).

4-Methoxy 5 methylhomophthalic Acid (IVd).—2-($\beta\beta$ -Dichloroethyl)-4-methyl-5-methoxybenzoic acid⁴ (IIIId) (5 g.) was added in small lots to 98% H_2SO_4 (40 ml) with same precautions as described in the case of (IVa) and the reaction was completed in the same manner. The solid separating on pouring the mixture on crushed ice was dissolved in sodium bicarbonate solution and the pasty mass remaining insoluble was removed. It was then reprecipitated and crystallised from aqueous methanol (charcoal) in prismatic rods, m.p. 205-207°, yield 2 g. On recrystallisation it melted at 208-209°. (Found: C, 58.90; H, 5.30; equiv., 116. $C_{11}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 58.93; H, 5.36%; equiv., 112).

4-Hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVe) was obtained by demethylation of (IVd) (0.2 g.) by heating with hydriodic acid (5 ml) and acetic anhydride (1 ml) in an oil bath at 130-40° for 3 hr. On pouring the reaction mixture in water, a solid separated. After triturating it with an aqueous solution of sodium bisulphite to remove traces of iodine, it was crystallised from water (charcoal) in plates, m.p. 213-14°, yield 0.1 g. (Found: C, 56.90; H, 4.40. $C_{11}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 57.14; H, 4.23%).

3-Trichloromethyl-6-hydroxy-5-methylphthalide (IIe).—3-Hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid⁷ (5 g.), chloral hydrate (6 g.), and H_2SO_4 (conc., 17 ml) were mixed and shaken well. After keeping the reaction mixture at the room temperature for 3 days, it was worked up as in the case of (IIa). It was crystallised from acetic acid (60-70%) in plates, m.p. 231-32°, yield 6.5 g. This substance was described by Meldrum and Kapadia⁴ as 3-trichloromethyl-4-hydroxy-5-methylphthalide (IIIf), m.p. 231-32°.

2-($\beta\beta$ -Dichloroethyl)-5-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid (IIIe) was prepared by reduction of (IIe) (5 g.) with zinc dust (3 g.) and glacial acetic acid (27 ml). The reduction was carried out as described in the case of (IIIa). It was crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. 184-85°, yield 3 g. This substance was reported by Meldrum and Kapadia⁴ as 2-($\beta\beta$ -dichloroethyl) 3-hydroxy-4-methylbenzoic acid (IIIIf), m.p. 184-85°.

4-Hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic Acid (IVe).—The dichloro compound (IIIe) (5 g.) was added in small lots to 95% H_2SO_4 (27 ml) with same precautions as described before and the reaction was completed in the same manner. The solid separating on pouring the mixture on crushed ice was first boiled with chloroform to remove the unchanged (IIIe) and then was crystallised from water (charcoal) in plates; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen, 213-14°, yield 3 g. This substance was reported by Meldrum and Kapadia⁴ as 6-hydroxy-5-methylhomophthalic acid (IVf), m.p. 213°.

Methyl Ether (IVd).—Dimethyl sulphate (1 ml) was added with vigorous shaking and cooling to the solution of (IVe) (0.5 g.) in aqueous NaOH solution (24 ml, 10%). After keeping it overnight, additional quantities of aqueous NaOH (7 ml, 10%) and dimethyl sulphate (0.5 ml) were added. Excess of aqueous NaOH (51 ml, 10%) was then added and the mixture was refluxed for 7 hr. It was then acidified with H_2SO_4 when a product separated which was crystallised from aqueous methanol in prismatic rods; m.p. and mixed m.p. with the specimen obtained above, 208-209°, yield 0.45 g.

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